

Species Composition, Relative Abundance, Monthly Fluctuation and Biodiversity Index of Phytoplankton in Mala River, Argungu, Kebbi State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The current research assessed the species composition, relative abundance, monthly fluctuation and biodiversity index of Phytoplankton in Mala River water in Argungu Town, Kebbi State, Nigeria. Collection of samples commenced from January to August, 2018. Three sampling sites were chosen from the river (Upper-stream, Mid-stream and Down-stream). Phytoplankton samples were collected from the sites and analyzed in the laboratory using standard protocol. Phytoplankton abundance and species diversity were determined by using Margalef, Evenness and Shannon index. This study identified 4 families of phytoplankton which include Bacillariophyceae, Chlorophyceae, Cyanophyceae and Euglenophyceae. Bacillariophyceae is the most dominant with the highest species composition of 3083 with relative abundance of 42%. It showed the total number of 22 different phytoplankton species. Highest composition was obtained in *Navicula digitoradiata* with 1744. While least composition was obtained on *Nitzschia acicularis*, *Turballaria fenestrata*, *Scenedesmus brasiliensis*, *Nitella brittlewort*, *Aphanocapsa ricularis*, and *Glococapsa punctata* with 13 composition each. It further revealed that, relative abundance of phytoplankton in Mala River depend on monthly fluctuation and sampling stations. Furthermore, results indicated that, highest relative abundance of phytoplankton was obtained at the mid-stream of the river in March (71.43%), February (66.67%), and August (66.67%). While least relative abundance of phytoplankton was obtained at down-stream in February, March, June and August with no any phytoplankton during those periods. Great biodiversity of phytoplankton in the study site and the species are evenly distributed. Further studies on physicochemical parameters and toxicological analysis of the Mala River are hereby recommended. The State Ministries of Water Resources and Environment should set up appropriate monitoring and controlling units to regulate sewage discharge into the river.

Keywords: Abundance, Argungu, Biodiversity, Composition, Mala River, Phytoplankton, Species,

1.0 Introduction

Water is a distinctive liquid that is basic for life and the most important means through which organisms can grow and develop. It serves as habitat for numerous organisms and no life can exist without water [1]. Water quality is a multifaceted subject that can be characterized clearly by physical, chemical, hydrological and biological (plankton and Microbial load of it) properties of water body [2]. Thus, quality of

water is, connected to the survival of all aquatic life in the water body [3].

Rivers are vital and vulnerable freshwater bodies that are critical for the sustenance of all life, providing main water resources for domestic, agricultural and industrial activities [4]. Any river system's quality is based on the complex relationships that exist between biotic (living things) and abiotic (non-living) elements in the river environment. The kinds of plants and animals that live in the river as well as the services it offers the neighbouring ecosystems are

determined by these factors. For the sake of the environment's well-being as well as the welfare of those who depend on rivers, it is crucial to comprehend and preserve their quality [5]. These rivers are important water resources that vary greatly in terms of their size and potential for fisheries [6]. The majority of the freshwater resources on Earth are found in rivers, which also greatly serve humans for irrigation and household use [7]. Thus, the requirement for phytoplankton variety and abundance in addition to the physical and chemical characteristics of water serve as important markers of both the quality of the water and the consequences of environmental change. Numerous categories of species, including fish, other animals, macrophytes, protozoa, and phytoplankton, have been researched upon to evaluate the quality of water [5]. To effectively manage aquatic ecosystems, it is imperative to understand the link between physical and chemical parameters and phytoplankton production. These factors impact the diversity and growth of phytoplankton, which can have an impact on the overall productivity and health of the ecosystem [6].

Phytoplanktons are tiny drifters plants-like wanderers organism, appearing as unicellular, colonial and/or filamentous forms, that move with the movement of water currents and are usually hanging or drifting in the upper sunlit layer of almost all oceans and bodies of fresh water on Earth [8]. They are vital indicators of water quality due to their ability to respond to environmental changes and short life cycles, hence, their composition indicate the quality of aquatic health. They are the most vital component for organic matter production in the aquatic ecosystem and are frequently found at the bottom of aquatic food web [2].

Phytoplankton study is paramount in water quality study, based on its importance in the productivity of a water body. River and other water bodies' status can be easily accessed on the bases of its phytoplankton distribution and composition. It is a major biological tool used in the assessment of the pollution and ecological status of river water and the variation provide an excellent indication of energy turnover in aquatic ecosystem due to its response to change in natural environment [9]. Certain phytoplankton species have the ability to emit noxious compounds including hepatotoxins and neurotoxins, which can be detrimental to both human and animal health [5].

Phytoplankton composition changes with nutrient fluxes because individual taxa have different requirements [10]. An important measure of water quality and productivity in a body of water is the quantity and quality of phytoplankton present. Accordingly, it is essential to keep an eye on phytoplankton populations in aquatic environments [5]. Therefore, studying the composition and diversity of phytoplankton is essential for understanding aquatic ecosystems and their productivity. This study highlights the relative abundance, monthly fluctuation and biodiversity index of phytoplankton in the Mala River at Argungu Town.

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 The Study Area

The study was conducted in Mala River at Argungu town. The river has its source from Sokoto/Rima River which has its original source from Sokoto and Zamfara States. Argungu is one of the urban towns in Kebbi State, Nigeria. As of 2007, Argungu had an estimated population of 47,064. The city is the seat of the Argungu Emirate, a cultural centre of state and one of the major agricultural towns, producing crops like, peanuts, rice, millet, and sorghum and cowpea. The town is well known for hosting Annual International Fishing and Cultural Festivals since Pre-Independent periods of Nigeria. The town is located at 12°44' N° 31' E / 12.733° N 4.517° E and is influenced by the local Sudan savannah climate. The rainy season starts from May ending and ends up in early October. The average annual rainfall density is 723 mm and the average annual temperature is 28.6 °C [11].

2.2 Study Periods

The study was conducted during the period of 8-months from January 2018 to August 2018. During the period of studies sample collection and analysis were done on monthly bases.

2.3 Sampling stations

Three sampling stations named as station A, station B, and station C along the Mala River in Argungu were used in this study and were selected based on stratified sampling method.

Station A is the upper- stream (source) situated at the upper level of the river, which was surrounded by grazing land and characterized by activities such as irrigation farming, cattle rearing, . Station B is the Mid-stream which is the middle level of the river where farming, fishing, bathing, clothes washing and transportation activities occurred. Station C is the down-stream, with similar characteristics with upper- stream which is surrounded by activities such as irrigation, farming, and cattle rearing.

2.4 Samples Collection

Monthly phytoplankton samples were collected in the morning between 08:00 to 10:00am using sampling bottles. After collection samples were transported to the Biology laboratory at Federal University, Birnin Kebbi, Kebbi state for Laboratory analysis. Phytoplankton samples were collected using plankton net of mesh size 55µm which were used to collect samples from below the water surface after towing for 10 minutes. The content was emptied into plastic container and fixed immediately with 4% formalin in the field for preservation [9].

2.5 Laboratory analysis

The collected phytoplanktons were allowed to stand for 24 hours after which the excess water is decanted. The samples were shaken very well and 1 ml of the sample was taken with a graduated dropping pipette and poured onto a counting chamber and covered with a slide. The prepared slide was viewed under the binocular microscope in the laboratory. The species were then identified and counted using standard identification schemes and manuals described by Omoboye *et al.* [12], Dhargalkar and Ingole [13] and Hydromet, [14].

2.6 Data Analysis

Data obtained in this study were presented in tables and figures. Indices were done as follows:

Relative abundance (RA): Relative abundance (RA) is the population of individual species divided by total population of species in percentage. In this study RA were evaluated using the formula adopted by Mahboube et al. [15]

$$RA = \frac{\text{population of individual species}}{\text{total population of species}} \times 100$$

Shannon Diversity Index (H): Shannon Diversity Index (H) is an index that is commonly used to characterize species diversity in a community. It accounts for both abundance and evenness of the species present. It is the proportion of species (i) relative to the total number of species (pi), and then multiplied by the natural logarithm of this proportion (ln pi). The resulting product is summed across species, and multiplied by -1 [15]. The higher scores show higher diversity.

$$H = - \sum_{i=1}^s P_i \ln P_i$$

Simpson's Dominance Index (D): Simpson's Dominance Index (D) is a measure of diversity which takes into accounts both the number of species per sample as well as relative abundance of the different species [15].

$$D = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1} n(n-1)}{N(N-1)}$$

Where: D = Dominance index, ni= number of individuals in the *i*th species, N = total number of entities in the dataset.

3.0 Results

3.1 Identified Families of Phytoplankton in Mala River

The identified families of phytoplankton in Mala River were presented in Table 1. These include Bacillariophyceae (7 genera), Chlorophyceae (7 genera), Cyanophyceae (7 genera) and Euglenophyceae (1 genus) (Table1). It further showed that Bacillariophyceae is the most dominant with the highest species composition of 3083 with relative abundance of 42%, followed by Chlorophyceae with species composition of 2863 and with relative abundance of 39%. Cynophyceae had species composition of 1053 with relative abundance of 14%, while Euglenophyceae had the least species composition of 413 with relative abundance of 6%. In addition the overall species composition observed in this study was 7412.

Table 1: Identified Families of Phytoplankton in Mala River

S/N	Families	Number of Genera	Composition of species	Relative Abundance
	Bacillariophyceae	7	3083	42%
	Chlorophyceae	7	2863	39%
	Cynophyceae	7	1053	14%
	Euglenophyceae	1	413	6%
Total		22	7412	

3.2 Phytoplankton species identified and their overall Composition of in the study area

The phytoplankton species identified and their overall Composition of in the study area are presented in figure 1 below. It showed the total number of 22 different species of phytoplankton which include, *Navicula digitoradiata*, *Scenedesmus brasiliensis*, *Oscillatoria aagrhdii*, *Euglena viridis*, *Rhopolodia gibberula*, *Westella botryoidea*, *Microcystis protocystis*, *Melosira varians*, *Ulothrix variabilis*, *Aphanocaps ricularis*, *Nitzschia acicularis*, *Ulothrix zonata*,

Glococapsa punctata, *Turballaria fenestrate*, *Nitella brittlewort*, *Rivularia aquatus*, *Paralia sculcata*, *Lyngbyaro busta*, *Sarcina ventriculi*, *Pseudonitzschia fraudulenta*, *Ankistrodesmus fusiformus* and *Crucigena crucifera*. Highest composition was obtained in *Navicula digitoradiata* with 1744, which is followed by *Lyngbyaro busta* with total number of 1445. While least was obtained on *Nitzschia acicularis*, *Turballaria fenestrate*, *Scenedesmus brasiliensis*, *Nitella brittlewort*, *Aphanocaps ricularis*, and *Glococapsa punctata* with 13 composition each.

Figure 1: Phytoplankton species identified and their overall Composition of in the study area

3.3 Phytoplankton species identified and their Composition at upper-stream of Mala River

Phytoplankton species identified and their Composition at upper-stream of Mala River are presented in figure 2. The results showed that 7 species of phytoplankton were found in the upper stream of the river, which include *Rhopolodia*

gibberula, *Westella botryoidea*, *Ulothrix zonata*, *Ulothrix variabilis*, *Lyngbyaro busta*, *Rivularia aquatus* and *Euglena viridis*. The highest composition was found *Lyngbyaro busta* (1445), which was followed by *Westella botryoidea* with 723 composition. While *Rhopolodia gibberula*, and *Ulothrix zonata* had the least composition of 13 each.

Figure 2: Phytoplankton species identified and their Composition at upper-stream of Mala River

3.4 Phytoplankton species identified and their Composition at mid-stream of Mala River

Phytoplankton species identified and their Composition at mid-stream of Mala River are presented in figure 3. It showed 11 species of phytoplankton which include *Navicula digitoradiata*, *Nitzschia acicularis*, *Turballaria fenestrata*, *Pseudonitzschia fraudulenta*, *Scenedesmus brasiliensis*, *Nitella brittlewort*,

Oscillatoria aagrdhii, *Microcystis protocystis*, *Aphanocaps ricularis*, *Glococapsa punctata*, and *Crucigena crucifera*. The highest composition was found *Navicula digitoradiata* (1744), which was followed by *Oscillatoria aagrdhii* with 923 composition. While *Nitzschia acicularis*, *Turballaria fenestrata*, *Scenedesmus brasiliensis*, *Nitella brittlewort*, *Aphanocaps ricularis*, and *Glococapsa punctata*, had the least composition of 13 each.

Figure 3: Phytoplankton species identified and their Composition at mid-stream of Mala River

3.5 Phytoplankton species identified and their Composition at down-stream of Mala River

Phytoplankton species identified and their Composition at dawn-stream of Mala River are presented in figure 3. It showed 7 species of phytoplankton which include, *Rhopolodia gibberula*, *Melosira varians*, *Pseudonitzschia*

fraudulenta, *Paralia sculcata*, *Sarcina ventriculi*, *Scenedesmus brasiliensis*, and *Ankistrodesmus fusiformus*. The highest composition was found *Pseudonitzschia fraudulenta*, (840), which was followed by *Scenedesmus brasiliensis*, and *Ankistrodesmus fusiformus* with 315 composition each. While *Melosira varians*, and *Sarcina ventriculi*, had the least composition of 15 each.

Figure 4: Phytoplankton species identified and their Composition at Down-stream of Mala River

3.6 Relative Abundance of Phytoplankton Species Observed in Mala River

Relative Abundance of Phytoplankton Species Observed in Mala River was presented in Table 2 below. The results revealed that *Navicula digitoradiata* had the highest relative abundance of 23.5% among the all phytoplankton species observed in this study, which is followed by *Lyngbyaro busta* with 19.50%. While *Nitzschia*

acicularis, *Turballaria fenestrata*, *Scenedesmus brasiliensis*, *Nitella brittlewort*, *Aphanocaps ricularis*, and *Glococapsa punctata* with relative abundance of 0.18% each. In relation to overall relative abundance in the sampling station, highest relative abundance of phytoplankton species was observed in mid-stream with 38.22%, which is followed by upper-stream with 35.8%, while down-stream had the overall highest relative abundance of phytoplankton species.

Table 2: Relative Abundance of Phytoplankton Species Observed in Mala River

S/N	Phytoplankton Species	Upper-stream	Mid-stream	Down-stream	Overall
	<i>Navicula digitoradiata</i>	0.00%	23.53%	0.00%	23.53%
	<i>Rhopoldia gibberula</i>	0.18%	0.00%	2.83%	3.01%
	<i>Melosira varians</i>	0.00%	0.00%	0.20%	0.20%
	<i>Nitzschia acicularis</i>	0.00%	0.18%	0.00%	0.18%
	<i>Turballaria fenestrata</i>	0.00%	0.18%	0.00%	0.18%
	<i>Paralia sculcata</i>	0.00%	0.00%	2.83%	2.83%
	<i>Pseudonitzschia fraudulenta</i>	0.00%	0.34%	11.33%	11.67%
	<i>Scenedesmus brasiliensis</i>	0.00%	0.18%	4.25%	4.43%
	<i>Westella botryoidea</i>	9.75%	0.00%	0.00%	9.75%
	<i>Ulothrix variabilis</i>	0.35%	0.00%	0.00%	0.35%
	<i>Ulothrix zonata</i>	0.18%	0.00%	0.00%	0.18%
	<i>Nitella brittlewort</i>	0.00%	0.18%	0.00%	0.18%
	<i>Lyngbyaro busta</i>	19.50%	0.00%	0.00%	19.50%
	<i>Ankistrodesmus fusiformus</i>	0.00%	0.00%	4.25%	4.25%
	<i>Oscillatoria aagrdhii</i>	0.00%	12.45%	0.00%	12.45%
	<i>Microcystis protocystis</i>	0.00%	0.51%	0.00%	0.51%
	<i>Aphanocaps ricularis</i>	0.00%	0.18%	0.00%	0.18%
	<i>Glococapsa punctata</i>	0.00%	0.18%	0.00%	0.18%
	<i>Rivularia aquatus</i>	0.35%	0.00%	0.00%	0.35%
	<i>Sarcina ventriculi</i>	0.00%	0.00%	0.20%	0.20%
	<i>Crucigena crucifera</i>	0.00%	0.34%	0.00%	0.34%
	<i>Euglena viridis</i>	5.57%	0.00%	0.00%	5.57%
	Total	35.87%	38.22%	25.90%	100%

3.7 Relative Abundance of Phytoplankton based on monthly fluctuations among the three Sampling Stations of Mala River.

The results of relative abundance of phytoplankton based on monthly fluctuations among the three sampling stations of Mala River were presented in figure 5 below. It revealed that relative abundance of phytoplankton in Mala

River depends on month and stations. The results further showed highest relative abundance of phytoplankton was obtained at the mid-stream of the river in March (71.43%), February (66.67%), and August (66.67%). While least relative abundance of phytoplankton was observed at down-stream in February, March, June and August with no any phytoplankton during those periods.

Figure 5: Relative Abundance of Phytoplankton based on monthly fluctuations among the three Sampling Stations of Mala River.

3.8 Spatial diversity indices of species in three stations of Mala River

The results of spatial diversity indices of species in three stations of Mala River were presented in Table 3 below. The highest number of taxa (11) was obtained in the mid-stream of the Mala River, while upper-stream and down-stream had 7 numbers of taxa each. In terms of species richness, highest species richness was found at mid-stream of the river with 1.258 richness. The Shannon (H) diversity indices revealed that species are more diverse at the upper-stream with an index of 1.117, which is followed by a down-

stream with a 1.515 index. While mid-stream species are less diverse (0.9536 indexes) compared to other parts of the river. However, down-stream had the highest dominance species with a Simpson index of 0.7307, which is followed by down-stream with an index of 0.6064, while mid-stream of the river had the least dominance species with Simpson index of 0.5144, while upper-stream and down-stream had 0.7609 and 0.7936 richness respectively. Based on evenness, species at the down-stream (0.6497 Evenness) are more evenly distributed compared to mid-stream (0.2359 Evenness) and upper stream (0.4367 Evenness).

Table 3: Diversity indices of Species Composition among three stations of Mala River

Indices	Upper-stream	Mid-stream	Down-stream
Taxa_S	7	11	7
Richness (Margalef)	0.7609	1.258	0.7936
Shannon_H	1.117	0.9536	1.515
Simpson_1-D	0.6064	0.5144	0.7307
Evenness_e^H/S	0.4367	0.2359	0.6497

4.0 Discussion

Water temperature, current velocity, nutrient availability, and light penetration into the water all affect phytoplankton abundance [16]. The characteristic patchiness of phytoplankton, which lessens the pressure from predators, is not even the reason for its dispersal in water bodies. According to Sharma and Bhardwaj [17], "nutrient availability, dynamics in water currents, and transparency all affect phytoplankton's temporal variation in abundance." Because planktons are so small, they have a high surface area relative to volume ratio. This link is significant because the creature can move more easily toward the surface because there is less frictional force between it and the water [2].

The present study determined the composition, relative abundance, monthly fluctuation and biodiversity index of phytoplankton in Mala River, Argungu Town, Kebbi State, Nigeria. Twenty-two phytoplankton species with a 7412 individual composition, belonging to 4 families were recorded in the Mala River. Similar families of phytoplankton were also reported by Abowei *et al.* [18], Ogbuagu *et al.* [19], Esenewo *et al.* [1] and Asuquo *et al.* [2] in Bayelsa State, Koluama River, Imo River, in Etche Local Government Area, Rivers State, Nwaniba River, South-South, and Mbiakong River, Cross River Estuary, Niger Delta, Nigeria respectively. The present results are also in accordance with the reported 38 species in Nasarawa reservoir by Yusuf [20].

Bacillariophyceae family was found to be the most dominant in terms of composition of phytoplankton species. This corroborates with the report of Hameed *et al.* [3] who also reported Bacillariophyceae as the family with highest species composition. Most of the phytoplankton species recorded in this study are common to many African freshwaters and have been documented to occur most especially in Nigerian reservoirs [3, 21]. Also in accordance with the study of study of Bonjoru *et al.* [5] who recorded Bacillariophyceae as the most dominant in terms of number of species in river Taraba at Garbabi, Nigeria.

However the study contradicts the study of Sharma and Bhardwaj [17], who reported abundance of phytoplankton in Ikere-gorge with Chlorophyceae (92.26%) as a dominant family. Also Ikenweiwe *et al.* [22] reported of a dominance of Chlorophyceae in Lekan-Are Lake,

Akin-Oriola [23] reported the dominance of Cyanophyceae, Omoboye *et al.* [12] reported family of Zygnematophyceae as the most dominance. The variation could be due to the geographical location and physicochemical properties of the river as reported by many studies.

The highest phytoplankton abundance recorded at the mid-stream of the river is unexpected considering the nature of activities (such as farming, fishing, bathing, clothes washing and transportation activities) taking place in the site. However, abundance could be due to high inflow of nutrients into the river from farmlands surrounding the river. These observations contradict the findings of Mishra *et al.* [24] on Bay of Bengal and Bolawa *et al.* [25] on Opa water body which had the highest phytoplankton abundance at the dam site basin as a result of less disturbance of water current and high transparency.

The study further revealed that relative abundance of phytoplankton in Mala River depends on monthly fluctuation and sampling stations. This is in line with the reports of George *et al.* [26] who also found great monthly and special variation on abundance of phytoplankton in Adiabo River in Calabar River system, South-South, Nigeria.

Margalef's indices provide information on the richness of species in an ecosystem. In this study, the maximum species richness was 1.258, and the minimum species richness was 0.7609, which are higher than the species richness reported by Bonjoru *et al.* [5] who obtained 0.35 as minimum species richness and 0.38 as the maximum by taking into account of both the total number of species present and the relative abundance of each species, the Simpson index is used to quantify the diversity of environments. More biodiversity in the sample was indicated by a higher value [3]. The study's Simpson index values, which varied from 0.7307 to 0.5144, showed that the species were dispersed equally (Evenly distributed). The Shannon-Weiner index (H') reflects both species richness and evenness, with higher values indicating greater species diversity. The values obtained are in conformity with the results of the studies conducted by, Brraich and Kaur [27]; Adelakun *et al.* [28] and Bonjoru *et al.* [5]

Generally, it has been determined that phytoplankton play a significant role in the bio-

monitoring of trophic status and water quality of aquatic ecosystem [29]. According to Ugwumba *et al.* [29], two noteworthy bio-indicator phytoplankton species observed were *Oscillatoria aagrdhii* and *Microcystis protocystis*. These species create algal toxins that have the potential to cause severe health problems for humans and certain other mammals. *Euglena viridis* is another pollution indicator species that was found in this study, indicating a possibility of pollution in the reservoir [3].

5.0 Conclusion

The present study revealed the presence of four different family groups of phytoplankton with Bacillariophyceae as the most dominant. And a total number of 22 different species of phytoplankton were identified with a composition of 7412. Highest composition was obtained in *Navicula digitoradiata* with 1744 with relative abundance of 23.53%. In relation to the sampling station, highest relative abundance of phytoplankton species was observed in mid-stream with 38.22%. It further revealed that relative abundance of phytoplankton in Mala River depends on month and stations. In addition the study revealed a great biodiversity of phytoplankton in the river. Further studies on physicochemical parameters and toxicological analysis of the Mala River are recommended. Also, studies that can establish the relationship between the physicochemical parameters and phytoplankton are recommended so as to know the overall status of the Mala River. It is also hereby recommended that further research on water quality as it affects phytoplankton, zooplankton and fish availability and distribution should be conducted. More so, The State Ministries of Water Resources and Environment should set up appropriate monitoring and controlling units to regulate sewage discharge into the river

6.0 References

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